

India – A Global Manufacturing Hub through Make in India – A Review

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturing is believed to be the key to the development of a nation. However in case of India it is the services which has spurred the development. Realizing the imperativeness of manufacturing sector 'Make in India' initiative was launched on 25th September 2014 by our Prime Minister, Mr. Narendra Modi. The new policy is launched with the objective of making India the manufacturing hub of the world (Gaubha et al. 2018). It also seeks to facilitate job creation, foster innovation, enhance skill development and protect intellectual property. The present paper is a review article, that focuses on how India will become a major manufacturing hub through Make in India that will be going to lead the world.

Key Words: Make in India, Development, Manufacturing

Introduction:

Make in India will boost foreign investments in the economy and on the other, Made in India will help the country being self-reliant in terms of manufacturing of products. Therefore, a logical route is needed to be adopted. It is being led by the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP), Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, of Industrial Policy and Promotion, the initiative aims to raise the contribution of the manufacturing sector to 25% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by the year 2025 from its current 16%. Make in India has introduced multiple new initiatives, promoting foreign direct investment, implementing intellectual property rights and developing the manufacturing sector. (Srivastava, 2019).

Manufacturing is believed to be the key to the development of a nation. However in case of India it is the services which has spurred the development. Realizing the imperativeness of manufacturing sector 'Make in India' initiative was launched on 25th September 2014 by our Prime Minister, Mr. Narendra Modi. The new policy is launched with the objective of making India the manufacturing hub of the world (Gaubha et al. 2018). It also seeks to facilitate job creation, foster innovation, enhance skill development and protect intellectual property. The logo of 'Make in India' – a lion made of gear wheels – itself

reflects the integral role of manufacturing in government's vision and national development. (Srivastava, 2019).

Many foreign companies making the investments in Make in India project thus having a great impact on the economy of India. India ranked 100 among 190 countries assessed by the Doing Business Team in the Ease of Doing Business Report, 2018 with an improvement of 30 ranks over its rank of 130 in the Ease of Doing Business Report 2017 (Srivastava, 2019). The government desires to achieve the growth of manufacturing sector by focusing on development of sectors like automobiles, power, railways, textiles, media and entertainment, aviation, leather, electronics etc.

The national program is designed to facilitate investment by eliminating red-tapism, promoting innovation by major bureaucratic reforms, deregulations and public-private partnerships. It targets to build best-in-class manufacturing infrastructure and enhance skill development so as to create environment favorable to that of setting up of business ventures in India. However, the vision though laudable is not easy to attain. There are a number of obstructions which the government will have to resolve before it can hope to achieve its dream of making India a global manufacturing hub (Gauba et al. 2018).

The Logo:

The **“Make in India”** logo is derived from India's national emblem. The wheel denotes the peaceful progress and dynamism – a sign from India's enlightened past, pointing the way to a vibrant future. The prowling lion stands for strength, courage, tenacity and wisdom – values that are every bit as Indian today as they have ever been (Srivastava, 2019).

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Policy:

The Make in India website defines the initiative as“a major new national program designed to facilitate investment, foster innovation, enhance skill development, protect intellectual property and build best-in-class manufacturing infrastructure”.

Objectives of Make in India :

The National Manufacturing Policy 2011 had set out a few objectives to be achieved in a long term period of 15 years. The objectives are as follows:

- Increasing manufacturing growth to around 12 to 14 percent.
- To make manufacturing sector the engine of growth for the economy.
- To develop manufacturing sector so as to enable it to contribute a minimum of 25 percent to the country's GDP by the year 2022.
- The policy also aims to create at least hundred million additional jobs in the manufacturing sector by the year 2022.
- To increase the global competitiveness of the Indian manufacturing sector.
- Ensuring stability of growth particularly with regards to environment.

- To develop infrastructure and invite state of the art technologies.

Literature Review:

The website dedicated to the „*Make in India*“ campaign describes it as - a major new national programme, designed to facilitate investment, foster innovation, enhance skill development, protect intellectual property and build best in class manufacturing, infrastructure. Experts in the industry pronounce manufacturing as the core of a country's economic development and job creation (Joon et al. 2013). As per the (Ghani. 2010) observation, the country India has a very different growth pattern. It has jumped directly from agriculture to services, side stepping the manufacturing sector.

India needs to concentrate on labor intensive manufacturing as that's where it has maximum comparative advantage. This becomes more imperative today when India is having one of the lowest economic growth since the past two decades.(Raheem , 2014). Manufacturing has the potential to provide large scale employment, because, in addition to forward linkages it also has strong backward linkages. (Kapoor, 2015) India is considered a challenging nation to start a new venture as its business environment presents too many barriers (Nally, Kapoor, & Juan 2015). Rigid licensing norms, elongated approval processes, poor infrastructure, stringent land and labor laws, were few of the many reasons, which ranked India at 142nd position among 189 nations in ease of doing business (World Bank Report on Ease of Doing Business 2015).

To meet the above, the Make in India initiative strategizes to simplify the laws and policies of doing business in India. (Sindhu, 2015). As a part of the initiative the government has already relaxed the FDI norms and increased its cap in various industries in controlled manner. Efforts are also on to make the county's tax system transparent and predictable. (Parthasarthy, and Agarwal 2016). Skill India is another project launched so as to have synergy between the objectives of the government, the industry and job (Das, 2015). No country in the world has achieved high-income status without developing manufacturing to a point where it accounts for at least a high share (around 30 per cent) of GDP. (Ghose, 2015). The dream of making India a global manufacturing hub, though, sounds very rosy but is full of challenges and roadblocks. Anarchic laws, tedious and costly land acquisition; rigid and inflexible labor laws are the three Ls that pose the biggest challenge to the successful implementation of Make in India (Jagannath, 2014).

The „*Make in India*“ initiative by the government that plans to create 100 smart cities are likely to further stimulate job growth thereby boosting more stability especially in the sectors like the manufacturing, engineering and automation (kher et al, 2016).

Need of the Study:

Make in India's success relies a great deal on the fate of the newer companies and start-ups. The new de-licensing and deregulation measures will surely reduce complexity and significantly increase speed and transparency. The digitalization of the procedures will make everything hassle free. Development of smart cities and industrial corridors will ensure that ideas get transformed into products. Skill development program will provide the necessary workforce to the entrepreneur (kher et al, 2016). Manufacturing is the key to increase in

income and better standard of living for developing economies. The government has started “Make in India” drive to harness the benefits of manufacturing sector.

Sources of Make in India Implementation:

Human Resource Development

India is expected to have one of the youngest populations in the world with about 65 percent of its people lying in the working age group. It is said that due to this demographic dividend (as it is popularly referred to as) India is expected to increase its annual growth rate by 2 percent every year. However, even though India has an abundance of human resource (which can be employed by the world over) there are some serious concerns over its employability. The human resource in India is mostly unskilled and the labor laws in India are quite anarchic. Both these pose a big challenge for the manufacturing industry development in the country (Gaubal et al. 2018).

Investment in Technology

Technology can play a pivotal role in reducing cost of operations, enhancing productivity, increasing growth and building a sustainable competitive advantage. Experts in the industry are of the opinion that only technology adoption and strategically leveraging will help Indian business houses to stay at par with their global counterparts and will also enhance their ability to deliver in the global market. Indian industries given the fact that we have leapfrogged with information technology and BPOs in the global services sector, still there are several hurdles before the Indian business before fully embracing the value, technology has to offer (Gaubal et al. 2018).

Land

Manufacturing of any product requires setting up of an industry which in turn requires land. India ranks seventh in the world in terms of total land area. Even with massive industrialization shortage of land is not expected in the country. There are quite a few precarious issues which prevent acquisition of land for industrial purposes; the most critical amongst them is small land holdings. Fragmented land means negotiation has to be done with multiple land owners which delays the entire land acquisition process; adding to this we have resistance and protests from social activists. Land acquisition for industrial purposes is cumbersome, risky and uncertain process in the country (Gaubal et al. 2018).

Micro, Small & Medium Sized Enterprises (MSME)

The Harvard researchers have predicted an average growth rate for Indian economy to be 7 percent annually for the next decade. They have also reported in their growth projections that the Indian GDP will be \$4.50 trillion on their calculation of measure for economic complexity. If we understand this in Purchasing power parity (PPP) used by IMF and World Bank; India's GDP will be at \$15 trillion. (Minhaz Merchant, Jan 2016). Micro, small and medium enterprises (MSME) will be the key players in progress path and support the development of new and modern entrepreneurs who in turn can create globally competitive businesses. The development of this segment is extremely imperative for the success of Make

in India Policy as it can significantly contribute to both manufacturing and employment in the country (both rural and urban). Overall, the MSME currently contributes 8 percent to the Indian GDP where as its contribution in most of the successful global economies is somewhere between 25 to 60 percent (Gaubal et al. 2018).

Infrastructure

India's growth has always been stifled by its poor infrastructure. One of the greatest threats that the industries in India face is that of chronic electricity shortage. Approximately one third of India has no access to it. Similar is the situation of roads and highways in India. Not much progress has been made in building of roads and highways with nearly half of county unpaved. This situation has to be handled on emergency basis when almost sixty percent of freight and nearly ninety percent of traffic is handled by roads. The quality of roads and highways is also disappointing and dismal (Gaubal et al. 2018).

The same inefficiency is seen in both development and management of ports in India. Currently the nation has seventy three major ports, out of which sixty are small and thirteen are major. Ninety five percent of external trade is handled by these ports characterized by cumbersome customs laws. Thus if the government wants the industries to make in India it has to ensure that at least the basic infrastructure like electricity, roads, railways, ports etc. are easy to access. To improve the infrastructure, the government should focus on public private partnership and open its doors to foreign investment (Gaubal et al. 2018).

Implementation of Make in India:

Make in India Initiative can be implemented through

By attracting companies from all over the world to India, the country will benefit from higher capital and technological investment. Young people in India will benefit from a dynamic economic environment to live and work in. „*Make in India*“ focuses on 25 different sectors of the economy, from automobiles and IT to chemicals and renewable energy (kher et al, 2016). In order to make India a manufacturing hub, Indian workers must have the relevant skills. Skills in the engineering, technology and science fields are especially sought-after nowadays to meet India's manufacturing ambitions (kher et al, 2016).

Two-year long apprenticeships with businesses are being developed to help the youth with their integration into the working world. Public-private partnerships help to establish the connection between education and employment. With a higher number of skilled workers, India will be able to compete with other countries (kher et al, 2016). With a more dynamic economy and many international companies setting up their manufacturing in India, young people will have access to more job opportunities. In a manufacturing industry that spans 25 disparate sectors, there is employment potential for a large number of workers (kher et al, 2016).

The growing number of international companies setting up in India means that infrastructure must be built to meet their needs and make the country as attractive as possible. India has often suffered from complicated business policies, ranking as low as 134 out of 189 in the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Index in 2014. Part of the challenge of the Make

in India initiative is to show that doing business in India is no more complicated. A dedicated portal has been set up to answer any questions about business policies in 72 hours. The E-biz portal facilitates applications for industrial licences, which have also been extended to be valid for a period of three years (kher et al, 2016).

Foreign Direct Investment:

In its endeavour to boost foreign investment in India, the current government has increased FDI limits in a number of industries like insurance and defence from 26 to 49 percent. Hundred percent FDI has been allowed in medical devices, telecom, single brand retail, asset reconstruction companies, construction, operations and maintenance of certain specific activities of railways. Many industries where FDI was already permitted have now been brought under automatic route like petroleum refining by public sector units, stock exchanges and depositories, power exchange (Gaubha et al. 2018).

Skill India Movement:

On the occasion of 'Youth Day' on 15th July 2015, our honorable Prime Minister launched 'Skill India' with the objective 'to make India the skill capital of the world'. Accordingly, the national policy on skills development and entrepreneurship 2015 was launched. The objective of the policy is to make the youth of India skilled with 'speed, standard (quality) and to link the skilled with the demand centers' (National Policy for Skill Development, 2015). However, apart from skill development emphasis should also be made to impart quality education to our students (Gaubha et al. 2018).

Development of Smart Cities:

The government has put in place the plan to develop hundred smart cities and modernization of existing mid- sized cities in the country. The smart cities would be equipped with high tech communication capabilities, twenty four hours water and power supply, public transportation along with walking and bicycle tracks, water and waste recycling. Government has currently allocated INR 7 billion (Kumar, 2015) (and more investment is expected from the private sector) towards this project. The plan for the first such city Dholera in Gujarat, is already complete and the process of land acquisition has been initiated. These eco-friendly cities which will, mostly be built along the Delhi Mumbai industrial corridor are expected to triple industrial output and double the employment opportunities (Gaubha et al. 2018).

'Make in India' initiative recent Policy changes are as follows:

- 100 per cent FDI allowed in the telecom sector;
- 100 per cent FDI in single-brand retail;
- Validity of industrial license extended to three years;
- For all non-risk, non-hazardous businesses, a system of self-certification to be introduced;
- Process of obtaining environmental clearances made online;
- The Government of India is developing the Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor (DMIC) as a global manufacturing and an investment destination utilizing the 1,483

km-long, high-capacity western Dedicated Railway Freight Corridor (DFC) as the backbone.

Make in India project has been started with the view to to generate employment, increase FDI and make India a manufacturing hub. There are numerous reforms which are imperative before India becomes a focal point of manufacturing. The slogan of zero defect products with zero effect on environment as given by Prime Minister will definitely realize the nation's dream of becoming a manufacturing centre for the entire world.

Benefits and Drawbacks of Make in India:

- Make in India initiative helps in creating jobs for ever increasing population of India.
- Conversion of India into a manufacturing hub of various commercial products.
- Development of the areas and the neighbouring locations where the industries would be set up.
- The program will boost the GDP of the Indian economy as foreign investments will lead to humongous flow of income.
- The FDI under this initiative would strengthen the rupee against the domination of the American dollar.
- As countries from all over the world will bring along latest technology, India will have an opportunity to make use of it as it lacks in various test mechanization.
- Setting up of industries under this initiative will help in the development of rural areas.

Drawbacks:

- Under Make in India campaign, all the focus lies on the manufacturing sector. So this causes a negative impact on the agriculture sector of India.
- As setting up manufacturing industries requires natural resources like land, water, etc on a large scale. So, there is a possibility of depletion of these natural resources which can threaten the survival of such large population of India.
- Entry of foreign countries into the manufacturing sector in India has caused a threat to the existing small local entrepreneurs and might force them out of business.
- A wide disruption in the agricultural sector due to the utilization of land primarily for setting of manufacturing industries.
- Tough competition leads to lowering of returns on FDI and results in outflow of capital from the economy.
- Unemployment will be created if the foreign investors back out from the initiative.

The development of the manufacturing sector will create employment opportunities for the youth of the country, alleviate poverty, attract investments, create value for Indian goods and fix the rising trade deficit. Internationally, it will improve India's standing in the world and investors will look at India not merely as a market but as an opportunity.

Conclusion:

India has the capability to push its manufacturing contribution to GDP to 25% by 2025. Government has to act as the central pivot of aligning industries, private companies, public sectors and all stakeholders in realizing this vision (Srivastava, 2019). Government

has to put policies in place be it sector reforms, labor reforms or the elimination of business barriers. The Government of India has taken a number of steps to further encourage investment and improve business climate. „Make in India “mission is one such long term initiative which will help to realize the dream of transforming India into a „manufacturing hub“ (Srivastava, 2019). Hon’ble Prime Minister’s call for “*zero defect and zero effect*” manufacturing resonates well with our industry as we grow and produce for the world. India’s expanding economy offers equal investment opportunities to domestic entrepreneurs and international players. It is our responsibility to leverage emerging economy (Srivastava, 2019).

The Prime Minister’s ‘Make in India’ campaign for a rapid manufacturing-led growth is the eventual outcome of the above evaluation. The movement not just endorses a rapid growth of manufacturing sector, but also advocates a lead role for manufacturing in India’s growth process. The campaign is expected to generate around hundred million jobs in the country. This will not only contribute to trade and commerce but also improve the living standard of the people and also reap other benefits of building manufacturing ability (Gauba et al. 2018). There is a long journey ahead of us and time is most opportune as to how much the government will be successful in this endeavor. The manufacturing industry has been ailing for many years and was neglected in the stride of development. This initiative has been launched to revive the manufacturing sector. The roadblocks of draconian business regulations, lack of consensus on land acquisition laws, shortage of skilled manpower still dodge us down. However, with government having shown the commitment to overcome these hurdles by introducing programs like e-governance, skill India, development of smart cities and various other industry specific initiatives there is light at the end of tunnel (Gauba et al. 2018).

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